

Pollen cryopreservation of bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia*) – An emerging technology for plant breeding and conservation

Anilkumar G S

Research Fellow, ICAR – Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hessarghatta, Bangalore, India

Abstract

Pollen cryopreservation is an important tool for the maintenance of male gametes and can promote improved efficiency in breeding and germplasm conservation and exchange. Previous studies in *Momordica* genus reported the threat of genetic erosion to a great extent. Hence, storing pollen for future use is an important tool in this genus in conserving genetic diversity. Viability by *in-vitro* germination assessment was carried by hanging drop technique using Brew-bakers media. Fresh pollen were packed in butter paper covers enclosed in sealed aluminum pouches and plunged into cryotank containing LN. The fresh pollens recorded maximum germination percentage of 78.25 % and it was 72.50 % after one week of cryopreservation with 10 % of sucrose in Brew-bakers media.

Objectives

- To assess the pollen viability, germination and feasibility of cryopreservation in bitter gourd
- Ex-situ* conservation of bitter gourd germplasm through pollen cryopreservation

Introduction

- ✓ Pollen play fundamental role in fertilization and consequently seed and fruit set in crop plants
- ✓ Studies on pollen germination and tube growth are both essential for understanding fertility problem in higher plants
- ✓ The success of pollen storage for genetic conservation purposes depends on many factors, and it is essential that the chosen procedure will ensure maintenance of high genetic integrity, vigour and germination percentages.
- ✓ Thus, it is essential to evaluate pollen viability before, during and after long-term conservation
- ✓ In this context, a study was conducted at Division of Flower and Medicinal crops, ICAR-IIHR, Bengaluru to check the pollen viability and feasibility of cryopreservation in *Momordica charantia*

Materials

Fresh pollen grains of bitter gourd, camlin paint brush, needle, butter paper, germination media, desiccator, cryo-bank facility

Methods

- The flowers buds are bagged one day prior to opening and collected in the next morning at peak anthesis time (7:00 am).
- Pollen extracted using camlin paint brush and collected in butter paper and kept for drying in desiccator to reduce the moisture of pollen.
- Viability by *in-vitro* germination assessment was carried by hanging drop technique using Brew-bakers media containing different concentrations (10, 15, 20 and 25 per cent) of sucrose solution.
- Followed by the fresh pollen were packed in butter paper covers enclosed in sealed aluminum pouches and rapidly plunged into the cryobiological system containing liquid nitrogen

Results and Discussion

- ✓ Fresh pollens recorded maximum germination percentage of 78.25 % and it was 72.50 % after one week of cryopreservation with 10 % of sucrose in Brew-bakers media.
- ✓ These observations ascertained that pollen cryopreservation is a safe and practical alternative for conserving genetic material that is often neglected by potential users

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Reference

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